

Jisc PID Agency: Focus Group Report

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Dr Fiona Murphy, MMC Consulting

orcid.org/0000-0003-1693-1240

Dr Phill Jones, Double L Digital Consulting

orcid.org/0000-0003-0525-6323

fiona murphy

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1 Executive summary

The Jisc PIDs for Open Access project is investigating approaches to the establishment of multi-PID implementations that can deliver tangible improvements to the research information ecosystem, and to ensure that the UK research sector has a strong and effective voice in PID development and governance.

As part of that wider project, in spring 2020 five focus groups were convened to build on the 2019 report *Developing a persistent identifier roadmap for open access to UK research*. The report outlined a series of proposed interventions. The objectives of the focus groups reported on here were as follows

- To take a deep dive into specific community issues, explore perceptions and elucidate needs.
- Validate the selection of five priority PIDs and the approach of a national PID consortium.
- Refine and prioritise the interventions outlined in the roadmap report cited above.

1.1 Key findings

Leadership - It is important to get questions of persistent identifiers into high level national strategic discussions. The UK government is currently conducting a consultation on its draft roadmap for research and innovation which affords a good opportunity. There was strong support for a UK multi-PID consortium. It was suggested that statements and actions of support by organisations like Jisc and UKRI would give the sector confidence. For example, adoption of particular PIDs associated with mandates attached to funding, and a communication campaign was recommended.

Governance - It is important to develop governance and sustainability models that allow for long term community engagement. There are examples of good governance that we can learn from. For example, ORCID was repeatedly mentioned as an organisation that, while not perfect, can be learned from. ROR was also singled out for praise on this point.

Prioritisation of interventions - The notion of prioritising specific interventions was broadly supported. In particular, we were urged to look at existing workflows for areas of overlap between the PIDs. Finding synergistic interventions can mean that improving the infrastructure or metadata associated with one PID can add value to the others. For example, adding Grant and Organisation IDs into DOI metadata for outputs solves a number of reporting pain points.

Outreach - There is a need to provide support, information and guidance to various stakeholders including institutional research administrators, librarians, researchers, funders, publishers and even PID-developing organisations. There is significant confusion around the difference between a grant and a project, the functionality that Crossref grant IDs provide and the capabilities of RAiD to support collections of works and practice based research. Engaging

academics in infrastructure conversations is challenging. They are best represented by academic associations and societies, particularly those with an interest in open research.

Individual reports for each focus group are in [Appendix A](#).

2 Focus group delivery

2.1 Process

Community feedback and sense-testing assumptions are all key features of the Jisc PIDs for Open Access project. Once the COVID-19 pandemic shut down opportunities to engage face-to-face, a plan was conceived to conduct five separate online focus group sessions - one for each of the priority PIDs - and thereby achieve the goal through other means. The sessions took place between late May and late June 2020 via Zoom. Consultants Drs Phill Jones and Fiona Murphy took participants - in groups ranging between four and ten in number - through a summary of the overarching PID project followed by a detailed group discussion. Using the specific PID as the focal point, the discussions explored the strengths, challenges and requirements for a PID-enabled research ecosystem that supports open scholarship. Meetings were recorded as well as notes taken. The results have been synthesised for this report.

2.2 Design

For maximum efficacy, it was important to establish a common understanding of the overall project, its rationale, objectives, and what the stakeholders were being asked for. Consequently, this strand of the PID project was introduced to the prospective focus group members as part of a community advisory body meeting.

1 April - team convened. Consists of Hilda Muchando. Victoria Moody and Adam Vials Moore (Jisc), Josh Brown and Alice Meadows (JAB), Fiona Murphy (MMC), Phill Jones (DLD).

The five focus groups cut drew from representatives from all stakeholders to aet the widest set of perspectives possible.

2-22 April - preparation for the stakeholder meeting. Invitees for the previously planned face to face meeting were re-invited, and some additional stakeholders, including representatives from publishing, were included in this round. A number of Jisc, UKRI and Knowledge Exchange colleagues also participated.

To ensure everyone had equal access to the project's progress to date, a detailed set of

briefing documents were circulated ahead of time. These included a briefing sheet about the meeting itself preparing participants to use the mentimeter polls, and outlining conduct around muting and questions.

23 April - stakeholder meeting held.

24 April - 27 May - focus group planning. The consultants provisionally divided up the stakeholder meeting attendees into five groups, taking care to have a range of functions within each. Emails were distributed. As well as scheduling the 90 minute sessions, they contained a survey to gather preliminary information about PID understanding, and offer the opportunity for group swapping. In the meantime, five separate slide decks, together with mentimeter polls (the outputs from which are listed in [Appendix B](#)), were developed.

28 May - 26 June - focus groups convened.

27 June - 31 July - synthesis, input to reports, the publishing plan and other activities, completing this report.

2.3 Attendance

Phill Jones and Fiona Murphy were supported by Josh Brown during each event. Hilda Muchando was responsible for communications and hosted the Zoom sessions.

Twenty-nine stakeholders from 19 different organisations participated. (There is a full list of organisations in the [Appendix C](#).) We had representatives from three different universities, a number of publishers and ORCID, DataCite, Crossref, the British Library, Wellcome Trust and F1000 Research.

An example of a menti question in action. Typed responses appear in parallel to a lively online discussion. The effect is like a virtual flipchart where everybody gets a marker pen.

2.4 Analysis and synthesis

In contrast to a face-to-face meeting, the online sessions provided an extremely rich seam of recorded data. Synchronous online note taking was supported by video and audio recordings, a lively chat conversation and the full menti inputs. These have all been collated, synthesised, discussed and reflected upon. Preliminary points and summaries have already been provided internally. While this particular document will remain internal and confidential, its findings will be fed into the second half of the project as well as providing the basis for various planned published outputs.

3 Implications for future project work

3.1 Workflow analysis

On the whole, the various focus groups were supportive of the workflow analysis that was presented in the [roadmap document](#) referred to above. In particular, while some stakeholders initially questioned whether there should be additional priority PIDs, contextualising the selection of the five priority PIDs in terms of the workflows for Gold and Green open access was seen as a strong justification for limiting focus to the 'priority five'.

Participants observed that the workflows rely fairly heavily on ORCID, which has higher take-up levels in the sciences than in the arts and humanities. Further, participants with an interest in the arts, humanities and practice based research felt that the workflows generally favoured scientific outputs. It was also observed that PID supported workflows are not just about giving labels to things but also involve creating a system that allows an interested party - whether they are a PI themselves or a research administrator looking for context - to ask interesting questions. At the same time, the system itself can be updated to increase automation, thus reducing burdens and enabling better decision making.

During the Outputs focus group session, participants were asked to list the types of objects that should have identifiers. Most of the suggestions aligned with DataCite's controlled vocabulary of output types. Notably, most other suggestions were collections of works including exhibitions, performances, portfolios and even all the outputs associated with the creation of a building. During the project ID focus group, we explored the idea of using project IDs for collections of works. It became clear during that discussion that there is a general lack of understanding of what a project ID such as RAiD could achieve for practice based research.

The need for education around project identifiers emerged again in the grant focus groups. It became clear that the distinction between a grant and a project is not well understood currently. This finding should inform outreach and education efforts.

3.2 Governance and Sustainability

Governance was discussed in all of the sessions. There was a strong preference for the governance of PIDs and of any PID consortium or agency to be community led. However, there was no clear sense of what ‘community led’ consists in practical terms. The risk of dependency on single groups or commercial entities was of significant concern in terms of sustainability and trust. There was recognition of the tension between the fact that research is conducted globally as opposed to setting up a national initiative but this was not considered to be insurmountable. In fact the concept of a single, national point of potential intervention could be helpful. At the same time, there was some concern that an agency would need to be led by a body with a deep understanding of PIDs and a stewardship remit. The long term preservation plan for the PID registries themselves has to be baked into the governance from its inception in order for it to be workable. The limits of its remit also need to be well defined. Several of the focus groups urged us to look at examples of community governance that work well already. ORCID, ROR and DSpace were given as good examples.

4 Refinement of targeted interventions

A number of suggestions were made to refine the targeted interventions. These are listed below

Leadership and strategic action

- Make use of ROR, rather than ISNI as the institutional identifier of choice. This preference is driven by ROR’s relative responsiveness to community input and more developed governance structure.
- RAiD has expressed an interest in working with Jisc. This represents a strategic opportunity to share in the first mover advantage and potentially establish a new revenue generating service.
- There currently exists an opportunity to discuss these issues at the national strategic level as the UK government is conducting a consultation on its roadmap for research and innovation.
- UKRI and Jisc should explicitly and publicly adopt certain PIDs as a means to drive adoption by example. The greatest uncertainty in the community surrounds Crossref grant IDs, and RAiD. By making specific PIDs mandatory wherever possible and attaching them to funding, there is an opportunity to show strong leadership.¹

¹ Having said this, while ‘mandating’ was preferred in the written contributions, the verbal exchanges tended to pull the consensus closer to the ‘educating’ school of thought.

Understanding the implications for interventions

- Using the Open Access publication workflow as a starting point, look at the points of intersection - where changes to one PID can have knock-on effects to raise the value of other PIDs - rather than simply treating each PID as a discrete entity. For example:
- Including a grant PID in the metadata of an output PID enables easier tracing of the impact of funding.
- Prioritise interventions that are not UK specific, as these will transfer to other countries more easily and help establish the UK's leadership position.

Outreach

- Update ORCID's value proposition for institutions to include taking ownership of their impact narrative, the better to show their value and enable them to influence discussions around issues like ranking.
- Develop the narrative around RAiD to include portfolios and collections of works and develop case studies based on project based narratives.
- Encourage the use of RAiD to identify practice based outputs for example in the REF, as a solution to link rot, lost outputs, and the 'REF graveyard'.
- Educate the community on how Crossref grant IDs work and how they differ from project IDs.
- In outreach efforts to researchers, focus on reducing administrative overhead as a practical and immediate value proposition.

An approximate representation of a PID-enabled research information workflow. This image is based on the workflows described in Developing a persistent identifier roadmap for open access to UK research <http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/id/eprint/7840>

5 Recommendations for the project

Relative prioritising

Questions asked at the stakeholder workshop included a vote on which of the five PIDs should be prioritised. Here is the result:

We asked the stakeholder meeting attendees: What would be your priority order for these PIDs?

The priorities expressed here mirror the respective levels of knowledge about perceived maturity of particular PIDs. That is, DOIs for outputs and ORCID for people are far better known than RAiD for projects, and better understood than either ISNI or RoR for institutions, or Crossref Grant IDs. Interestingly, the ordering seems to be a rough inverse of the number and severity of pain points that were raised in the focus groups. There may be a level of cognitive bias at work here, whereby people tend to prioritise the problem that they know the most about.

In building narratives and messaging, it makes sense to leverage the higher ranked PIDs to increase understanding and usage of the lower ranked. In other words, the reason for messaging - and specific audiences - will vary according to the PID. For example, information about output IDs may be less about the DOI concept itself and more about what could be considered an 'output', with perhaps a different approach in the humanities, which have been less exposed to DOIs than the sciences. Meanwhile, organisation ID information might be about which PID is best to use and how to find or register it, and project ID messages are likely to require clarity on what a 'project' actually is and why you might want to use a PID in relation to it.

The missing stakeholders

The stakeholder workshop attendees were also asked who was missing from the room. 'Researchers' was overwhelmingly the most frequent response. The debate around researchers being the invisible centre of all these types of discussions was touched on during all of the focus groups and there was general agreement that this absence always represents a deep challenge: researchers generally and understandably wish to spend time on their research rather than on the systems that underpin it. Librarians and other research support managers usually act as researcher proxies, but given how closely involved the PID strategy is with the research ecosystem, additional effort may need to be made to maximise the PID project's chance of building engaged support. Learned societies - particularly those with

interests in publishing and open scholarship - are likely to be the most suitable bodies with which to interact. Possibilities include The Royal Society, Institute of Physics, British Ecological Society, Microbiology Society and others.

Appendix A - Individual Focus Group Reports

Person IDs

Attendees

- Jisc
- Hindawi
- F1000Research
- British Library,
- F1000Research,
- RORI

Introduction

This group felt that ORCID is now established as the *de facto* Person ID for academia due to its wide recognition and comparatively good governance structure. Consequently, much of the discussion was spent trying to synthesise what has so far been learned by ORCID in its journey towards acceptance and from ORCID's usage patterns. However, there was also recognition that different disciplines and stakeholders have had very varied levels of take up. Furthermore, there are calls for more extensive uses to be made of the ORCID functionality throughout the research ecosystem to truly benefit open science.

Governance

It was pointed out that it is important to get questions of persistent identifiers into high level national strategic discussions. Now is a good time to be having these conversations as the UK government's research and innovation roadmap was recently released for consultation². This puts Jisc in a good position to have an impact on issues like the potential dilemma between national strategic priorities and global community needs. Further, the existence of an integrated national funding mechanism in the form of UKRI, provides a single point of intervention thereby enabling more integrated, agile thinking and decision making.

We need a way to identify the key parts of the infrastructure that are fundamental to the research workflow and find a way beyond simple membership models of achieving long term sustainability and governance for them. A certain amount of 'the community will decide' is required, which necessitates being very clear on who the 'community' is made up of and what the community thinks.

² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-research-and-development-roadmap>

Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier (ORCID)

Thomson Reuters (now Clarivate Analytics) launched the Researcher ID in 2008. However, adoption of their proprietary solution was patchy and the identifier itself was not open or fully interoperable, which led the wider community to look again at this issue. ORCID, which was based on code donated by ResearcherID, was launched in 2012 and has emerged as the de facto standard person identifier for those currently active in the research space. ISNI still sits alongside ORCID, but although it has some uses - such as being the ORCID equivalent for attributing the outputs of deceased researchers, or for those who are active outside the research sector - it has failed to rival ORCID's market penetration.

Adoption

Given that ORCID is comparably well established, much of the discussion was about how to use ORCID to accelerate the acceptance, awareness and adoption of other persistent identifiers. However, there was also conversation about building on knowledge and best practices around ORCID. Perhaps specific work around Plan S, the Open Research Funders Group, SPARC and RORI would be helpful to support its adoption?

There was also however, a recognition that adoption has been slower amongst the humanities than by the STEM disciplines. This may be cultural, or because there isn't an easy way to add ORCIDs to research input fields at appropriate points in the workflows. Practice-based Research (PbR) is itself a complex issue. To support uptake, there's a need to reduce friction throughout the system at every touch point.

Sometimes adoption can be slowed within institutions because the people in charge of the institutional infrastructure systems, the CRIS or the repository, do not have sufficient bandwidth, incentives, technical resources, or training to be able to make the best use of the system under their supervision. Updating the reporting frameworks to clarify what is required, together with additional training, may help.

Moving forward

Owing to the importance of keeping the momentum and importance of this work through the government mechanisms, the senior research officers involved should be keenly aware of key opportunities to contribute to policy and information gathering exercises. To be long-term sustainable, the PID strategy needs to be adequately understood, supported with well-researched government policies and resourced as a high priority by national bodies such as UKRI or BEIS.

ORCID's value propositions should be updated to take into account institutions' own priorities, including their ranking concerns, understanding of their own value, taking ownership of the impact narrative, and eventually becoming more proactive on how ranking itself is conducted.

Organisation IDs

Attendees

- DataCite
- British Library
- Jisc Expert Group

Introduction

Research organisations have an obvious and critical role in the research infrastructure as both trainers and employers of researchers as well as the administrative and physical home for many research projects. On an individual level, researchers' home institutions have long been a matter of prestige and reputation. In recent times, the growing importance of strategic research management on an institutional, national and regional level, and drive towards open research, has brought into focus the need for a unique persistent identifier for institutions.

The Organisations focus group discussed questions around governance and sustainability of the PID consortium in general. On the specific question of organisation IDs, the group discussed the challenges around driving adoption and the relative merits of ROR and ISNI as PID solutions for organisations.

Governance

The group did not come up with a definite suggestion for a governance structure but instead highlighted its urgency. One participant said:

... governance and sustainability are crucial to long term persistence. Working on sustainability should lead to community governance via a long term sustainable cost recovery model. Without that we fail, so for me it is imperative.

One participant wondered who would 'own' the consortium on behalf of stakeholders and whether it would be self-sustaining financially or funded as part of an organisation. They noted the excitement around DORA, for example, but asked whether it's financially robust.

ORCID was flagged as an example of a sustainable structure for PID governance leading to the suggestion to look at existing organisations that do this well.

Adoption

To achieve adoption, the group felt that organisational IDs need to be adopted throughout the lifecycle of research. Only then can the value be maximised. This leads to a collective action problem. The group suggested that Jisc, UKRI and other national level organisations could show stronger leadership here. A strong signal of national level adoption could be the spur that institutions, publishers and funders need to get on board.

ROR vs ISNI

There was a rigorous discussion of the relative merits of ROR and ISNI. While ISNI is well established and has wide coverage, it is felt that there is a governance concern or gap, and a lack of consolidated community involvement.

ROR was noted to have the inverse set of challenges. There's community support, governance and momentum. It is also open source and has an open API. On the negative side, it is not very granular and does not cover private organisations.

Overall, the sense that ROR is heading in the right direction seemed to be the most prevalent among the group. It is more important that the governance enables flexibility so that it can follow emerging needs.

Moving forward

There was a suggestion that defining the appropriate form of governance for an organisation PID isn't possible until the function is understood. A participant said:

It's important to look at medium and long term requirements. Look at what we have now and will it still be relevant in 3 years time. We need to map the requirements for each of the stakeholders and discover where we have matching requirements.

Another said:

We need flexibility, and need a solution that will solve community problems rather than stand in the way of problems being resolved.

The conclusion was a recommendation to look at the points of intersection between an organisation ID and other persistent identifiers, prioritising the interventions that add the most valuable functionality to the whole system and identifying easier wins through improving user experiences such as workflows. To do that, ROR emerged as the best option because it has appropriate technical interfaces, community engagement and a governance structure that will allow it to develop to meet the community needs identified by the group.

Grant IDs

Attendees

- Cardiff University
- Imperial College London
- Microbiology Society
- SocPC
- Jisc
- Crossref
- ARMA
- HESA
- STFC

Introduction

The group began by identifying the need for an integrated strategy that goes beyond supporting compliance with Plan S and explores the long term governance and sustainability of the PID infrastructure. Particularly with respect to Grant IDs, effective systems have to be built and integrated to support all relevant workflows that are important to stakeholders or there will continue to be problems with low adoption.

There were discussions around driving the conversation on a global level while maintaining a UK strategic focus as well as the need to invest in education and outreach, particularly for poorly understood PIDs like Crossref Grant IDs and RAiD.

The group had questions about how Crossref Grant IDs work and felt they needed to know more before they could say if they were a functional solution. On the other hand, there was a clear view of how funders could take a leadership role around a grant ID of some sort that could drive adoption of all PIDs.

Global impact

On the subject of balancing UK strategic needs with the global needs of scholarship, the theme was simplicity. The less UK-specific the interventions, the easier it will be to get others to follow. It was suggested that we reach out to organisations like INORMS to get a global perspective on research management needs as well as Gates Foundation, the US National Institutes of Health, Chan Zuckerberg Foundation and the Chinese Academy of Sciences.

Vendors of RIM and CRIS systems support global communities, and may also be useful partners. By working with commercial (EG Symplectic, Pure, Converis) vendors as well as

non-commercial groups (EuroCRIS³, PTCris⁴, IRIS⁵) to incorporate standards for identifiers, it might be possible to normalize the use of Grant IDs to drive penetration.

The need for education and outreach around Grant and Project IDs

Despite the fact that the people in the room were chosen as well-informed members and leaders of the PID community, there was a self-acknowledged lack of understanding of both the nature of Crossref Grant IDs and RAiD. Going further, there was also a lack of understanding around the difference between a grant ID and a project ID.

While there were no concrete objections to the Crossref Grant ID system per se, and in fact, Crossref was praised for making effort in this area, there was a reluctance to voice support for it purely out of a lack of knowledge of its functionality and metadata. A number of questions were typed into the mentimeter page ranging from querying how well it supports multi-funder grants and grant extensions to its potential integration with financial systems.

Driving adoption

A participant shared that they had been informally A/B testing explanations of grant PIDs with researchers and found that explaining it as a way to make life easier for mandatory reporting created more interest than explaining the relevance to open research or the research infrastructure. This highlights the need to take a value-driven approach to the value proposition and messaging.

Extending the logic to funders, it is important to communicate a clear value proposition, preferably with working use cases or case studies. It seems to be unclear to many funders how the adoption of a Grant PID would make it easier for them to collate and track the input of the work that they fund. Explaining how this will work is key to the long-term success of this project.

The group agreed that funders occupy a very influential position in the research management and evaluation landscape. By adopting a Grant PID, mandating its use and working with partners such as research management systems vendors and publishers, a funder such as UKRI could set a powerful precedent and exert significant pressure on the ecosystem.

³ <https://www.eurocris.org/>

⁴ <https://ptcris.pt/>

⁵ <https://iris.unime.it/>

Project IDs

Attendees

- British Library
- Teeside University
- University of Kent
- Jisc
- ARMA

Introduction

Project PIDs polled as the lowest priority in the April stakeholder meeting. One possible reason for that low polling may be a lack of understanding of what project IDs are and how they might help the community. This lack of understanding was illustrated in the focus group by considerable discussion about what projects are as well as what they are not. In particular, the distinctions between projects and grants were debated in detail, concluding that projects can be connected with multiple funding grants, publications, or instruments - or none at all. Since projects are complex and compound, rather than discrete, entities, the PIDs used to reference them need to have the flexibility to work as an envelope while recording the complex, and changing, relationships between the entities both within and without it. For the purposes of research integrity, project management, career reporting, impact assessment, and other critical administrative and analytical functions, the group added that understanding the 'envelope' can be as important as understanding any of the individual entities contained within it.

The Project ID group discussed issues around governance and sustainability, and research(er) evaluation. The Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) was explored as a possible option.

It was recognised that the term 'Project' is applicable not just to scientific lab outputs but also to the humanities. More than any other of the PIDs under discussion in this project, the Project ID's focus is on linking other PIDs together and deriving understanding about their relationships.

Governance

Similar to other PIDs, there needs to be clarity on what sort of organisation would be required to govern project PIDs themselves. In addition, the multi-stakeholder nature of projects drives a specific concern over who has control over managing the metadata associated with a given project. What would the boundaries be? How would control be passed on over time? There were also questions around how to scale, as this could quickly become very complex.

Adoption

It was generally agreed that mandating specific policies, such as the compulsory use of PIDs in certain circumstances, would be less effective than possibly developing a global policy, concordat or best practice that institutions, organisations and even individuals could sign up to (something like [the FAIR Data Commitment Statement](#) was suggested). This approach would then frame emerging practices as more than 'mere' administration and present a better opportunity for academic and research manager buy-in.

One person raised the question of how you might mandate use of Project IDs:

Is the burden on researchers, or are the tools they're using compliant, in which case it's for the vendors to tackle?

RAiD

Although some attempts have been made in this space - via PID Graphs (Freya) and the CERIF data model, RAiD is the first community-led persistent identifier to be developed specifically to serve projects. It is therefore at an early stage, and the developers are keen to work with Jisc. As noted above, there are some critical questions around scale and control that still need to be addressed and there is an opportunity with RAiD to help with the framing of what is required. Mindful of previous issues with complexity, RAiD is seeking to be lightweight and flexible.

Moving forward

More work needs to be done to clarify what Project IDs represent as well as their potential usefulness. Ultimately it could cut down administrative burdens, and build trust in a greater range of research outputs as whole projects, their connected outputs, people and grants and the full provenance remain clear in the longer term. (This point was prompted by the experience of going back to old REF submissions and realising how many broken links were impeding full understanding of the outputs and impact.)

Build a compelling narrative for why implementing the Project PID is important. The implementation itself needs to be made functionally simple. Perhaps work could be done with behavioural psychologists to understand and adapt to sharing behaviours and social concerns.

There is also the issue of trust. When it first launched, Google presented such a step change in the way that the internet could be navigated that trust was instilled as an instant feedback loop. What can be done to facilitate such a process with PIDs, which involve no such instant reward? The fact that your data disappears when you input to systems works against the building of trust. Is there a way to provide a quick - even instant - win?

Talk to researchers about what constitutes useful bodies of work to treat in this way. How do different disciplines work with the model?

A case study could start by using a grant to define the project and then follow it through. This could take a long time so if retrospective work could be achieved that would help.

Output IDs

Attendees

- Wellcome Trust
- DataCite
- ALPSP
- RCA
- CoSector
- OASPA

Introduction

Research outputs are an important concern for a persistent identifier strategy. While Crossref and the DOI standard are well established in the scholarly infrastructure, there is a growing sense that a number of issues are yet to be addressed. Challenges around multiple versions of research articles as well as multiple copies of versions have emerged. The term outputs here extends beyond research articles and books to include the myriad of objects associated with research activity including but not limited to unstructured and structured research data including objects like sequences and atlases, computer programmes, figures, protocols, grey literature and posters.

The outputs focus group discussed a potential tension around optimising workflows for the types of outputs that are most strongly incentivised today - articles - and influencing the way that assessment is carried out and what is valued to be more inclusive of outputs from the arts and humanities.

Challenges around technical expertise and resources for both smaller institutions and smaller publishers were raised as barriers to adoption and best practice. The creation of a consortium was thought to be a potentially effective way to spread the burden.

Appropriate breadth of type of outputs

An interesting discussion arose around the breadth of types of outputs that should be identified and recognised. A member of the group suggested that the PID project itself was too focused on research articles, and to a lesser extent, books. In particular, practice-based research was said to be underrepresented both in the infrastructure as it stands today and in the proposed interventions. One participant spoke of a REF graveyard.

A lot of work goes into packaging up all outputs, but particularly practice outputs into what's called a portfolio ... often, then it gets lost and there's no longevity to it. Something like a PID could help people find that in the future.

As a counterpoint, another member of the group argued that research articles still carry the most weight in terms of academic assessment and so for strategic impact reasons, should be the initial point of focus. There was a perceived tension between improving the workflows as they stand today, and changing the system to more equitably account for outputs from the arts and humanities.

Governance

The theme in discussions of governance was that other organisations have put work into this and should be studied and we should use what's there. In terms of governance for output related projects, a participant felt that DSpace was quite far along and doing well.

The need for community governance and openness was highlighted as a way to develop resilience and prevent dependence on any particular organisation.

What types of outputs should be accounted for?

A broad range of output types were suggested:

Visual art, Performances, Datasets, Software, Designs, Policy and advocacy, Workflows, Outreach activities, Buildings/centres, Film, Sound, Speeches, Performances/plays, exhibitions, conferences, and collections.

For reference, the current list of DataCite objects is:

Audiovisual, Collection, DataPaper, Dataset, Event, Image, Model, InteractiveResource, PhysicalObject, Service, Software, Sound, Text, Workflow^[P?]_[SEP]

The suggestions of output types that need to be covered maps well to what DataCite already supports. A number of participants suggested output types that are really collections of one form or another. A project ID like RAiD offers a way to refer to groups of outputs and so care must be taken that the right sort of PID is used for new types of objects.

Driving adoption

Some participants were surprised to hear that many repositories don't follow best practice around Handles and DOIs. Strategies to address that were suggested. On a technical level, something similar to the DNS network that self-propagates was proposed. On a cultural level, it was thought that getting repositories to report their level of DOI adoption and create a sense of virtue around good PID practice may help.

Challenges for small organisations around lack of resource and technical expertise hinders the adoption of PIDs. Particularly, there's a fear of the cost of maintaining PIDs. This is true both for institutions and publishers. For example, the need for publishers to update DOIs with new URLs creates a point of failure, particularly when journals change hands.

The idea of a consortium was thought to be helpful in spreading the burden of both creating the infrastructure and maintaining the metadata for all stakeholders.

Appendix B - Menti Outputs from Focus Groups

Please note that the outputs below are unedited and are not corrected for spelling or grammar.

Person IDs

Some disciplines (often in the humanities) show lower levels of adoption of ORCID. How do we account for this?

Less places for an iD to be used / collected

Complete lack of awareness

Humanities outputs take different forms from STEM disciplines. For example, they may release a book chapter every year for discussion, but not formally publish for years.

Without decent publishing workflows ORCID is less useful - big STM publishers find this easier than small HSS ones

more caution about govt tracking

Culturally incompatible (dislike of being reduced to a number)

Humanities outputs may not have identifiers that interoperate with ORCID automatically.

less focus/understanding of metadata in general except fo e.g. digital humanities

Lack of integrations means lack of value for Humanities scholars. Hence lower adoption.

Infrastructure not always reflects work and outputs (including orcid item types)

In some disciplines reporting is not the concern of the scholar themselves, therefore a personal identifier that aids reporting doesn't make sense to them

Lack of vendor system support

Vendor systems are super expensive

Not every institution has implemented ORCID. What are the barriers to uptake?

Lack of local systems that would benefit combined with lack of funds, expertise and resource

Lack of FTE / expertise

Vendor systems do not always support ORCID

Vendor systems can be super expensive.

Requires cross-organisation consensus to implement

CRIS system support tends to be seen in countries that have joined up national reporting frameworks

no resources for outreach education/training for staff about ORCID

No champion at pvc level

benefits only realised if all institutions adopt - collective action problem

limited understand by Institutional leaders

Efficiency IF systems properly set up - requires infrastructure buy in but then saves lots staff time e.g. Money

What are the primary benefits (value proposition) that we should focus on when persuading institutions to more fully embrace ORCID?

Understanding the activity of their staff

Making their reporting more accurate

Making it more likely outputs are affiliated with their institutions

Reporting and demonstrating research impact

tracking scientific and societal impact of the university for the university

working out who their researchers are collaborating with and where -

Efficiency IF systems properly set up - requires infrastructure buy in but then saves lots of money!

ability to counter the usual institutional rankings with counter examples of specific, context dependent benefits

Ability to better demonstrate its own value.

How can ORCID be made to better meet the needs of researchers and institutions in order to drive uptake?

Lower the barrier to entry

More automation for researchers

An improved 'new user journey' to help researchers get the most out of their record

Embed in workflows to drive automation / prefill

More automation via more integrations in more disciplines.

More integrations across systems and workflows

make ORCID profiles public by default

It's a second order problem - more things taking advantage of ORCID - but also ensuring ORCID records are complete by making update easier / simpler

increase trust in reliability of ORCID - that it is who it says it is etc

Consider supplementing ORCID metadata with data from other sources, so that integrators don't have to 'shop around'.

ORCID drives efficiency in workflows best when connected to other PIDs. How can this be maximised?

identify the other PIDS, whose implementation will best showcase the benefit of ORCID to target group (institutions, funders, researchers) - e.g. RoR and grant IDs

Consider supplementing ORCID metadata with things from other sources, so that integrators don;t have to 'shop around'

Better UX in visualisation of landscape for scholars and institutions

Lobbying integrators to do more

get publishers and institutions and funders etc to use ORCID as the means for single sign on to multiple interoperable systems (speaks to integration)

Somehow get the publishing systems and manuscript submission systems to consider ORCID as important enough to communicate about and use to update ORCID records.

national policy alignment for ORCID

Organisation IDs

Organizational IDs have struggled to gain traction and adoption. Why is that?

Implementation throughout the lifecycle

No mandate?

Aligning processes for all stakeholders

Too much choice. Needs one solution to be mandated or adopted as the main solution at a national level.

Embed identifiers into workflows

Different use cases require different levels of granularity

The PID roadmap project has identified 2 strong candidates for a PID for organizations. ROR and ISNI. Are there others we should have thought of?

Or should there be a fresh start?

UKPRM is not a strong candidate because it's nationally focused

What are the pros and cons of RoR?

+community governance

Pro - Not just research organisations but includes FE colleges, Hospitals and funders

Con - It lacks granular department level.

What are the pros and cons of ISNI?

+ve established, coverage

-ve community involvement, lack of governance, slow setting these up

- ISNI/Ringgold cost model doesn't encourage uptake

For an ID candidate, what's more important? Governance? Sustainability? Integrations? Current level of adoption? Something else?

They're all interconnected and equally important

It must do what is needed and then have governance and sustainability to ensure it continues

It does need to have flexibility

Maybe the work on use cases comes first? ie what is the demand/want?

Minimise data entry at each stage. Automate as much as possible.

What should we consider when conducting use case evaluations? Is there anything missing from the use case workflows in the roadmap document?

Ease of implementation

Impact

Interoperability

Must work for research in business and third sector as well as HEI/

Worst case scenario and best case scenarios/ Scenario mapping

Minimise data entry. Automate the process as much as possible.

Mandate for automation improvement?

Grant IDs

Further comments about the suitability of Crossref Grant IDs?

Most platforms already know how to integrate with crossref

What are the concerns people have?

Needs more adoption by funders, and system integrations.

Not familiar enough with specifics of Crossref Grant IDs

Makes the information openly available.

CrossRef standard seems fine. Adoption is the issue.

Do we need DOIs or another type of PID (something new?)

I don't know specifics, but agree with feedback that they exist, which is a better start than nothing. More awareness among stakeholders clearly needed.

I'm not well sighted on Crossref's suitability but the fact that it has traction already is surely enormously important.

Need to have integrations with key systems in order to make their use friendly to relevant stakeholders, including researchers themselves.

Cross ref Grant IDs not well enough known by research management community

Lack of knowledge

I don't know how Crossref Grant IDs deal with things like grant extensions, supplements, how they relate to projects and groups of grants etc.

I'd be reassured about the suitability of Crossref as an ID provider if there was a set of objective criteria that might be applied to any PID provider against which they could be tested.

Observation - an emerging distinction between the technical branding of an underlying PID, such as 'DOI' and a market branding such as 'Grant Id', 'Natural Science Identifier', etc. As PIDs become more widely adopted for different purposes there can

Can Crossref ID handle grants made jointly by multiple funders? Long term rolling grants?

Overview of metadata schema for Crossref grant IDs would be helpful

Has the Finance community been engaged with the suitability of CrossRef Grant IDs, separate to Research Managers? In terms of Financial reporting, they will have specific requirements, if they get what they need from it=extra business case

How do we convince/incentivise funders to participate?

Make it easy.

Efficiency in research and for the REF

Reporting!

Good use cases they can relate to

Show benefits of networked PIDs - they can track the outputs of their funding

Outputs and outcomes reporting is a huge agenda for funders so I would have thought the incentive in reporting this would be clear for funders

Clear description of the benefits to them

Improved ability to report on impact of their funding

Clear description of how it can be easy to integrate into their systems

Improved compliance with Research Fish returns and improved data quality in these returns

Tasha- completely agree- machine learning over metadata is the future

Identify where the best current practice is happening with funders and highlight the benefits that are accruing to them. And then make that practice clear and visible to other funders and foster a climate of competitive best practice

Make it simple to do

research grants come from many sources so UKRI might not be enough?

Pain points: Administrative overhead on mandatory returns. Hard to collate the impact of the work they fund. Data is incomplete.

Some funders give out small grants - learned societies. It's hard to evidence those over a lot of small grants.

Shows ORCID holders have been given grants.

Quality of reporting and financial efficiency

What barriers to entry might we find for funders?

Lack of technical understanding

Integration with their own systems, some of which are old and dreadful

Systems

Reporting infrastructure doesn't exist yet!

Will they be backing a winner?

Ability to agree an approach across funders

Challenge of getting their systems to integrate/ interoperate with it

Technical +1

want the community to recommend the solution rather than top down

Inertia and lack of capacity/capability to change workflows

Lack of management buy in

What's the quick win?

lead-in time/competition against other projects and implementation of other identifiers

Absence of a clear conceptual connection between the reporting problems and the technical solutions

Who should we partner with to provide grant discovery and linking tools?

I've never seen a Crossref Grant Id so I'm assuming they're just another DOI?

Are we clear about the distinction between grants and projects? (not specific to Crossref grant ids)

The community of Research managers who manage grants generally respond to funder requirements, they don't care too much about outputs or open access (rightly or wrongly). They respond to requirements from funders.

Overview of metadata schema for Crossref grant IDs would be helpful

CRIS & RIMS vendors

Suppliers of research management systems (CRIS and Grant Management)

Cris vendors

Tools like dimensions

Vendors of editorial/ peer review/ submissions tools used by publishers

Do we discriminate between commercial and not for profit?

Publishers

Publishing platforms e.g. Atypon

Any entity that is creating descriptive metadata for research outputs - publishers, metadata creators etc.

What challenges might we encounter when working with partners to integrate grant discovery and linking services?

Time constraints

Low priority compared with other projects

Question of chicken and egg, who goes first? Where does critical mass have to be created before others get onboard?

Everyone will want everyone else to adopt it first

Some vendors might want to use their own data.

Commercial suppliers are led by their community user groups, so those communities have to be engaged

Costs and buy-in

Agreement as to pathway

Insufficient benefits case to prioritize the project high enough

How do we make this a high priority for them given everything else they have to do?

Metadata creators work to incredibly tight timings for creating records. Any friction or too many clicks means it won't make it into the workflow.

The question from them is likely to be 'do customers want this?'

Funders need to adopt it first to provide an incentive to platform providers.

Needs to be embedded.

Project IDs

Project identifiers are a new category. What's your current understanding of the benefits of project IDs?

Keychain model to hang project rather than funded or pi centric information and narrative

To tie elements of work together. Then we can link outputs to funding / internal projects

Impact - eg in REF case studies for eg or I'd/ data doi/ grant itD

Ability to define what a project is, where its limits lie and how it has changed over time.

To make them more FAIR (certainly findable and accessible)

Linking funding data outputs outcomes

Yes... the persistence is a REALLY important part - thanks Victoria

Agree with Victoria - a great umbrella ID

Yes - If the PID can also be linked to all the other items (cf CERIF data model) then the data are so much richer.

What are the requirements of a project identifier? 'projects' could be a loose term. EG scientific research, a building, or an art performance.

The Identifier... you mean the associated metadata...? cf CERIF again

Project ID system needs to be extensible to new types of entities and PIDs as they are established.

A parent or a child project

Ability to contain objects added with chronological context

Lots of the CERIF stuff though is largely untested (I think)... and the semantics need to be pinned down. But all of these things are "extra" to the actual PID

Clarity in the definition of what a project is.

Work packages within projects cf grant processes?

To me... PID... is what is needed.... maybe dates... other than that... other data items are surely in the links... "is part of another PID", "is led by [person]" "is located in [building]" ...?

PID, Name, Start Date... (End Date)

Need to be able to represent portfolios

Portfolio... = collection of PIDs.

.. that is all

What types of entities could a project identifier like RAiD describe that might be less obvious?

Anything...!

Your research focus question

Analysis code please

Working groups

Narrative journeys

Instrument usage

Unfunded research

Agree with Steph... Funding is an optional item

Collection level pids

Disagree with Steph... all projects are time limited... eventually all the PIs ... die
TV programmes, YouTube channels, tweets, all kinds of other public engagement content

Researcher/research group web pages - if they have a few different research areas of interest, they could have a RAiD for each area of research

Trademarks the whole IP space

Events

Exhibitions

Yes resolution of project.... could be a work package... a project... a programme... need to have an PID at the resolution that might want to be linked to

Patents

Is there' stuff that shouldn't have pids?

Thanks Steph! ;-) [re collections]

What needs to be considered for a sustainability model around RAiD?

Funding

Needs governance... some body (or bodies) to manage and maintain

Curate carefully- not everything

Consider previous Q on who/what is responsible for maintaining each record/PID

Needs to have "community" but-in involvement

Good question... who "owns" the PID is *really* important
eg - clear for ORCID... not so much for PID

Scalability

Looking at the pilot approach in the briefing document, what does the consortium need to consider in its approach?

Western/developed bias?

If you want to show it's more than just a STM research initiative, *start* with the humanities pilots and use cases

National vs international initiatives & directions of travel

I like the idea of starting with AHSS

and yes, agree with Josh, need to have the international picture firmly in mind - and looking at what they are doing and their experience

Different ontologies across disciplines (as well as workflows, outputs, funding levels...)

Saying 'global' early adopter engagement in the paper and then only names Oz, NL and US is a bit painful. Understand there aren't many early adopters, but calling that 'global' is my problem.

AAS and Wellcome are running a number of capacity building projects

Output IDs

Plan S principles call for PIDs for scholarly pubs and 'relevant entities'. What are the output types and needs other than articles?

Visual art

Performance

Datasets

Software

Collections and exhibitions

Designs

Policy and advocacy

Workflows

Objects

Impact/Esteem

Outreach activities?

Buildings/Centres

Sound

Film

Performances, plays

Speeches

Conferences

Bodies of work

Do we need different types of identifier or will the DOI cover it? If so, how do DOIs need to change to support other output types?

Connectivity

Update DOI metadata schema to include all relevant outputs

Depends on how flexible the meta data structure is

Meta-DOI for a collection or body of work of things that each have their own DOIS

When there isn't a central object like a research article. Should there be an overarching object to represent the collection. Can it be done with metadata.

Successful integrations leading to a network effect

How can we better standardise the use of PIDs in repositories?

Automate

Successful integrations leading to a network effect

The PID equivalent of a DNS network where records propagate?

Accessibility by all users, regardless of size, funding, resource, infrastructure

Get repositories to report how many objects have PIDs. How PiDful is your repository. A report card?

Mandating their use. Voluntary gets you only so far

The DOI for a document remains fixed over the lifetime of the document, whereas its location and other metadata may change. Referring to an online document by its DOI is supposed to provide a more stable link than simply using its URL.

But every time a URL changes, the publisher has to update the metadata for the DOI to link to the new URL. It is the publisher's responsibility to update the DOI database. If they fail to do so, the DOI resolves to a dead link leaving the DOI useless

What considerations need to be taken into account when trying to improve persistence and standardize practice in the 'long tail'? Where do we start?

Financial implications

Not an equal playing field - smaller institutions have less resource, infrastructure, funding

How mandatory PID generation is

ISBNs - need to think about the other stakeholders

Because textual outputs are seen as the norm, non-textual outputs are often not the priority for larger, STEM-focused institutions.

What incentives are there to provide PIDs? For both the researcher and the orgs generating them.

In some small institutions, there aren't enough domain experts in research-focused librarianship.

Open source standards

Demonstrate benefits

Looking at the example workflows in the roadmap document? Are there any refinements or questions that you have? What did we miss?

Very article focused

Workflow starts with ORCID - little incentive for practice researchers to engage with this in the way that researchers who produce textual outputs find it incentivised.

The link between outputs linking to grants and specific projects

What's the initial impetus to connect to ORCID?

Very orcid focused

What about people who aren't science or artists? Community leaders, members of the public etc.

There needs to be a mechanism for changes like URL changes to propagate.

Appendix C - Organisations represented

1. British Library
2. STFC
3. Wellcome Trust
4. University of Kent
5. Imperial College, London
6. University of Cardiff
7. Royal College of Art
8. OASPA
9. ARMA
10. HESA
11. ORCID
12. Crossref
13. DataCite
14. SocPC
15. F1000 Research
16. ALPSP
17. SilverChair
18. CoSector
19. Jisc